

THE PRESENCE OF PETROBRAS IN THE REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF BAIANO

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ABSTRACT

The present work intends to discuss the role of Petrobras in the regional development of Bahia. Based on the literature review on the role of the oil industry in regional development and an empirical analysis of data that support the effects of the industry in the region, the main objective is to analyze the role of the oil and gas industry, under Petrobras, in the state of Bahia, between the years 2000 to 2021, aiming from a historical perspective to identify the contribution of this company in promoting the regional development of the state and the possible impacts with its departure. Thus, among possible results, it is expected that this study can propose an answer about the unexplored potential of the oil and gas sector for the economic and industrial development of Bahia, during the investigated period; rekindle the debate about the insurmountable “Bahian enigma”; to point out promising paths for the oil and gas sector, but still unexplored from the perspective of regional development.

Keywords: Oil and gas industry; Petrobras; Regional development; Bahia.

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the oil and gas industry in the economic development of nations is undeniable. Since the middle of the 20th century, oil has become the most coveted commodity in countries, firstly because it is a raw material capable of generating useful products, such as gasoline, aviation kerosene, oil for domestic heating and industrial fuel oil (YERGIN , p.911,

2020), and second, because it is a product that moves a long production chain, and requires high investments, technological development, skilled labor, among others. In other words, having an oil industry or being part of its production chain is a positive premise for the economic development of countries.

In Brazil, the implementation of the oil and natural gas industry not only allowed national economic development, but also used this sector to promote industrial and technological development, in addition to guaranteeing national energy security. All this being orchestrated by the State through Petrobras. Since its creation (1953), the state-owned company has sought to consolidate itself as an integrated industry, present throughout the national territory, promoting research, qualification of labor and stimulating innovation in the entire production chain through programs financed in most cases by Petrobras itself. .

While recognizing the relevance of the oil industry within the national context. It is necessary to analyze this industry at the regional level, recognizing the particularities of each region and identifying whether the simple fact of having an oil company installed in the region is a guarantee of economic development.

GOAL

To analyze the role of the oil and gas industry, under the influence of Petrobras, in the state of Bahia, between the years 2000 and 2021, aiming, from a historical perspective, to identify the contribution of this industry to regional development and the possible impacts of its exit.

THEORETICAL APPROACH AND MAIN ARGUMENTS

According to Piquet (2012), the development of a regional economy based on the oil industry depends on the capacity of its industrial park and its productive and economic complexity. If the region does not have supplier sectors, which comprise the oil production chain or has minimal capacity, the multiplier effects of the oil industry will tend to occur externally, from the importation of products and services with the necessary qualification.

In cases where there is formation of an oil production chain, it is possible to observe great economic fragility. Because it is a sector that is highly dependent on the international scenario, therefore, any change in demand or external supply that implies the oil trade, will have impacts on the region that has black oil as its main product. Another factor that negatively

influences the regional economy is the volatility of oil prices. Its innumerable variations can make the region's economy increasingly dependent and fragile.

Still according to Piquet (2012), the development of the region through the oil industry will depend on which segment it is inserted. Regions whose participation is concentrated in the upstream segment of the production chain tend to generate expectations regarding a “positive economic inflection”. However, in this case it is necessary for the region to have an innovative industrial capacity and promote intersectoral linkages, as in this segment the activities carried out are highly intensive in capital and technology.

In the case of regions focused on the downstream segment, there is greater capacity for “positive economic inflection”, as the activities carried out enable productive diversification and intersectoral linkages in the oil industry. However, it is necessary for the government to direct policies and investment to this end, as this is an activity that has little liquidity and high risk, it is difficult for private capital to enter without being provided with incentives or partnerships with the government.

Another factor to be observed with the presence of this industry in the region is the workforce, although it creates the expectation of an increase in job creation, there is a low level of absorption of local workers. Due to the activities of the production chain demanding highly qualified labor, when this local offer is not found, companies tend to seek to supply this demand with workers from other regions, resulting in an exponential increase in the population, followed by the marginalization of the local population.

As of 2016, with the new political reorientation of Petrobras, many of the regions of Brazil no longer have the state-owned company operating in their territory and with this, the space was opened to discuss the relevance of the state-owned company in the regions. Although it is still a recent process, some effects can already be felt. Taking the Northeast region as an example, where Petrobras offered for sale nine shallow water oil and gas production fields located in the states of Bahia, Sergipe, Rio Grande do Norte and Ceará, it sold Gaspetro (responsible for the distribution of natural gas in the region), the closure of activities at the Quixadá biodiesel plant, in Ceará, the sale of the Regasification Terminal in Bahia de Todos os Santos and two thermoelectric plants, in addition to the sale of RLAM (currently Mataripe), it can be seen that there was a strong disarticulation of the industrial complex, many of the companies that had the raw materials supplied by Petrobras units as guarantees, now have to resort to other states, or are hostages of the private monopoly exercised by the companies that acquired the units. It is also noticed, an increase in unemployment and a reduction in income

generation, many of the state-owned workers were fired and those who were hired by the current companies receive lower wages.

In addition, there is a fiscal impact with the closure of activities, municipal collections should be drastically reduced, as royalties and taxes linked to oil activity have a large share in the collection of producing municipalities, reaching in many cases a participation of around of 50%.

In summary, we can say that the presence of the oil and gas industry in a given region can be very favorable for economic development, however, it is necessary to have a parallel political planning of regional development linked to the national one. Otherwise, the presence of industry in the region will be unable to develop productive linkages with pre-existing sectors.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology to be worked on in this research is characterized as explanatory, with quantitative analysis through the use of primary data.

For this, it will make a literary review focused on the issue of regional development regarding the implementation of the oil industry in a given region, and the multiple effects caused by these. Based on studies by authors such as Denise Terra, Frédéric Monié, Oswaldo Guerra, Ron Boschma, Rômulo Almeida, Rosélia Piquet, among other thinkers.

Starting from the concepts presented by the reference authors, the work will analyze the role of Petrobras in the regional development of the state of Bahia between the years 2000 to 2021, as it is a period that includes: an expansionist phase of the sector (2003-2014) and another divestment phase (2015-2021), resulting in the sale of the refinery.

For this, it will be necessary to survey data corresponding to the number of dwellings, population, income, employment, GDP, among others, published and produced by IBGE, ANP and RAIS, which allows us to analyze the social and economic impacts of the oil and gas industry. in the state. It is worth mentioning that for data referring to income and employment, this research will adopt the groups: 06.00-0 (Extraction of crude oil and natural gas), 09.10-6 (Activity to support the extraction of oil and natural gas), 19.21 -7 (Manufacture of Petroleum Refining Products), and group 19.22-5 (Manufacture of Petroleum Refining Products) of CNAE 2.0 to ensure a better analysis of the economic importance of this industry in the regional economy.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

As initial considerations, the oil and gas industry is very promising for regional development, but its success will depend on which segment the region is inserted in, the industrial capacity of the region, the ability to generate productive diversification in the state, generation labor, among others.

It is also worth noting that the absence of political planning for regional development associated with national planning prevents the oil industry from developing a greater capacity for productive drag on the pre-existing sectors in the states.

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